

THE PROBLEMS OF INCREASING THE LEVEL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE OF JUNIOR COMMANDERS (SERGEANTS) OF BACK-FRONT UNITS IN THE CURRENT ARMY OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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**A Big Guide To The Supply Cycle
Sergeant Iii Class**

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Annotation: The processes of labor development of the cultural capital of military sergeants who are serving under a contract are considered. Growth trends are revealed not only for potential cultural capital, but also for its professional accumulation.

Keywords: military service, training, method, behind the front, sergeant.

It is important to identify how, in the context of the transformation of the social and socio-economic structure of society, cultural capital undergoes substantial changes, to clarify the main trends in the professional accumulation of specific knowledge, career growth, consumer practices of the individual.

It is well known that as the degree of satisfaction of needs for material goods and services increases, the range of needs themselves expands, a tendency is manifested to their elevation and ennoblement. And in this our hypotheses are confirmed by a number of researchers. So, Ch. Barnard proposes to consider human abilities as a result of the development of the needs of a working person. The social and labor development of employees of organizations (in our case, military organizations) provides for the constant development and implementation of projects for the labor accumulation of the cultural potential of employees, the development of the educational communication component of labor interaction between members of the organization. The labor activity of the employees of the organization should increasingly include a spiritual innovation component. We meet similar conclusions in J. E. Mayo, who argues that in addition to the formal organizational structure, the modern organization has signs of a social informal structure. Therefore, in the new conditions, labor activity, in addition to physical labor, increasingly includes a spiritual component, which develops in the context of improving consumer practices.

We study the labor sphere of servicemen in the context of the formation of their professional cultural capital. Qualitative changes in the system of professional labor activity will reflect a number of directions in the development of the professional cultural capital of servicemen.

1. The development of professional cultural capital and career growth - qualitative changes in the system of "objective professional movements" of contract servicemen.
2. Transformation of labor consumption - qualitative changes in the system of "objective orders for labor" of contract servicemen.
3. Increase in income - qualitative changes in consumption, the manifestation of the factors of benefit in the use of the potential cultural capital of contract servicemen.

Thus, servicemen define the process of education and professional retraining, as well as labor motivation, as the main factors in the growth of professional competence. At the same time, the number of respondents who focus on the need to develop the entire complex of material and non-material factors of labor motivation is growing. If at the beginning of military service,

non-material factors of labor motivation are considered as a factor in the growth of professional competence by only 0.79% of military personnel, then in the process of military service, the composition of adherents of complex motivation increases to 7.94%. It is proposed to activate the following intangible factors: to improve not only working conditions, but also the entire system of life of individuals, to develop and implement a number of intra-organizational educational projects aimed at increasing professional competencies.

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